

EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF METHODOLOGICAL
COMPETENCE IN FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

Sobirova Oygul Alimovna

doctoral student of Kokan SPI

Abstract. In this article, there are detailed comments on experimental work related to the development of methodical competence in future music teachers. Also, the article contains thoughtful opinions on the implementation of experimental work and the mechanisms of its implementation.

Keywords. Scientific research, experimental test, respondent, pedagogical practice, methodology, analysis, lesson development.

ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНАЯ РАБОТА ПО РАЗВИТИЮ МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ
КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ МУЗЫКИ

Собирова Айгуль Алимовна

базовый докторант Кокан ГПИ.

Абстрактный. В данной статье даются подробные комментарии экспериментальной работы, связанной с развитием методической компетентности будущих учителей музыки. Также в статье содержатся продуманные мнения по поводу проведения экспериментальной работы и механизмов ее реализации.

Ключевые слова. Научное исследование, экспериментальная проверка, респондент, педагогическая практика, методика, анализ, разработка урока.

Introduction. In any scientific research, the compatibility of the proposed theoretical ideas is studied by organizing a test case aimed at ensuring their initial application to practice.

Therefore, it is important to organize experimental work based on the theoretical idea recommended for pedagogical practice and methodical developments that ensure its application to the educational process. Consequently, the necessary pedagogical conditions required for the rational solution of the chosen scientific problem are created by means of experimental work.

In the framework of relevant research, the organization of experimental work, implementation in experimental areas and analysis of the obtained results, in order to come to a certain conclusion, educational and special, as well as literature on the organization of the teaching process, created on the musical sciences taught at the Higher Education Institution, ideas put forward in research on vocal performance. was accepted as the main source of information.

The information supply for the organization of experimental work aimed at the development of methodological competence in future music teachers was formed on the basis of the following: the purpose, tasks, main stages of the experimental work, objective and subjective factors affecting the effective and successful organization of the experimental work, fields of experience and from them, the respondents-students involved in the trial work, as well as information about the scientific and pedagogical methods used in the trial work.

Analysis and results. One of the most important conditions for the successful organization of scientific research is the clear definition of the goals and tasks of experimental work.[1.P.136]

The purpose of the experimental work aimed at ensuring the investigation of the research problem was defined as the improvement of modern methods and innovative technologies for the development of methodical competence in future music teachers.

It was assumed that the main result of achieving the set goal will be determined not only by knowledge, but also by having methodical knowledge at the level of practical application, creative approach, and analysis.

The achievement of the purpose of the trial work was ensured based on the positive solution of the following tasks:

1. Development of an experimental program representing the practical implementation of theoretical ideas related to the development of methodical competence in future music teachers.
2. Selection of modern didactic methods and technologies found to be effective for the

development of methodical competence in future music teachers.

3. Formation of a special methodology for the development of methodological competence of future music teachers with the help of selected modern didactic methods and technologies.

4. Multi-stage testing of a special methodology aimed at developing methodological competence of future music teachers based on the organization of experimental work.

5. Evaluation of the level of development of methodological competence of future music teachers based on summarizing, analyzing and processing the results of multi-stage tests using the mathematical-statistical method.

As in any process, pilot work consists of several stages that complement each other consistently. One of the steps acts as a "foundation/ceiling" for the other.

Experimental work was organized in the following main stages in 2021-2023:

1. Grounding experiment phase (I half of 2021) - at this phase, the purpose of the experimental work was determined; on its basis, the scientific and pedagogical tasks that need to be implemented were determined; Pedagogical conditions were created to achieve the goal of the trial work and to effectively solve the specified scientific and pedagogical tasks (for example, the experimental areas were selected; the number of respondents involved in the trial work was determined from them; the involved respondents were conditionally divided into two groups - experimental and control) by random selection were divided into groups; the respondents were informed about their participation in the test work and their tasks; in order to ensure the consistent, continuous and systematic organization of the test work in the experimental and control groups, practical pedagogues were selected and attached; practical pedagogues involved in the test work were given information about their tasks during the experimental period; future music In order to study and evaluate the current state of development of methodological competence among teachers, a primary diagnostic test based on pedagogical observation, questionnaires and test questions, and quantitative analysis was organized).

2. The formative experimental stage (II half of 2021 - I half of 2023) - at this stage, based on the results of theoretical analysis, a program of experimental work was developed, allowing the effective development of methodological competence of future music teachers, innovative methods were selected, the authorship of the researcher special methods were formed based on the approach; a special methodology for the development of methodological competence of

future music teachers was developed using the methods based on the selected innovative and authorship of the researcher; in the process of organizing the experimental work, partial changes were made to the content of the special methodology, taking into account the situations (problems, existing difficulties) that were noticed in the practice of music education; the test program was put into practice on a large scale in experimental areas.

3. Emphasis (summary) experimental stage (II half of 2021) - secondary diagnosis based on quantitative analysis of pedagogical observation, questionnaires and test questions, results of practical training in order to study and evaluate the situation formed after the experimental research aimed at developing methodological competence in future music teachers. trial work was organized; the results of the substantiating and emphasizing experimental work were summarized, and the final results were reanalyzed using the mathematical-statistical method (Student method); according to the results of the analysis, the effectiveness of the experimental work was evaluated and a final conclusion was reached.

Certain factors affect the progress of any process. It is divided into objective (external) and subjective (internal) factors according to its character and source.

The concept of "factor" means "reasons that affect the education or training process in one way or another". [2.P.24] Objective factors are "reasons that do not depend on the learner or the student, and subjective factors are "directly the learner or the student and his are the reasons that depend on the teacher (educator), as well as the surrounding persons and the activity of the educational institution". [3.P.43]

Based on theoretical analysis and observation of educational practice, it was determined that the influence of the following objective and subjective factors is important in the success of the experimental work aimed at developing methodical competence of future music teachers:

the availability of the necessary educational environment (educational auditorium, technical equipment) for the organization of test work in experimental areas; organization of the test process based on a well-founded program; that methodological developments related to the development of methodological competence among future music teachers have been prepared and that their content is of a high level (objective factors);

orientation of pedagogical contingent opportunities for consistent, continuous, systematic conduct of testing in experimental areas; researcher-practitioner-pedagogues-respondent-students

understand each other and treat each other with mutual respect; high-quality and complete performance of the tasks assigned by the practitioners-pedagogues involved in the test work; the respondent-students' activeness in the trial work; direct participation of the researcher in the test work and consistent control of the overall process; constant analysis of the current situation; the introduction of necessary changes to the pilot-test program based on analysis and mutual consultation as required by the situation; direct analysis of each stage of experimental work; that the test results are reasonable and reliable; that an unbiased conclusion was made based on the final results (subjective factors).

It is known that the main subjects of scientific research conducted in pedagogical and psychological directions are respondents, that is, persons involved in the test work (students in this study). Accordingly, the number of respondents participating in the test work in the selected experimental areas was determined (Table 1).

Table 1

The number of respondents-students involved in experimental work (by HEIs with experimental sites)

№	Fields of experience	Number of respondent-students
1.	Andijan State University (ASU)	76
2.	Tashkent region Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute	79
3.	Navoi State Pedagogical Institute (Navoi SPI)	81
Total		236

For this reason, the respondents-students involved in the test work from the experimental areas were assigned to the experimental and control groups by random selection (Table 2):

Table 2

Proportion of respondents-students involved in experimental work (by experimental and control groups)

№	Fields of experience	Number of respondent-students	
		Experimental groups	Control groups
1.	Andijan State University (ASU)	36	42
2.	Tashkent region Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute	41	40
3.	Navoi State Pedagogical Institute (Navoi SPI)	40	37
Total		117	119
Total		236	

In the course of the test work, the effectiveness of the special methodology aimed at developing methodical competence in future music teachers was studied at the two stages of the experiment - the grounding and emphasizing stages of the experiment and the situation observed in the control groups (students' possession of the relevant competence and its existing level), at the beginning and at the end of the experimental work. The difference between the two groups, according to its positive or negative character, represents the effectiveness of the special methodology and its suitability for practice.

There is a problem that has not yet been positively resolved in scientific research in the field of pedagogy. Practitioners-pedagogues from educational institutions with experimental fields are usually involved in the process for consistent, continuous and systematic organization of experimental work. The involvement of practitioners-pedagogues in the trial work is decided according to the personal initiative of the researcher, his relationship with them, and the researcher T. Ch. Aliboyev explains this problem: "This is where the question arises: if the methodologists involved in the trial work are not provided with a monthly salary, the teachers of the experimental areas will he agree to this? In fact, there is no legal basis for providing monthly salary to Methodists involved in trial work for independent scientific and pedagogical research. Therefore, mutual methodical cooperation is formed between the researcher and the methodist-teachers in the organization of the scientific-pedagogical experience. According to him, during the period of the emphasizing experiment, the researcher provides methodical teachers with

methodical developments in the relevant subject, and the methodical teachers, in return, help the researcher in organizing experimental work.

Based on the approaches of the author, the following tasks were assigned to the practitioners-pedagogues in the process of experimental work aimed at developing methodical competence in future music teachers: to ensure the activity of the respondent-students in the test work; introduce them to the nature of the experimental work, the role and tasks of the respondents in this process; ensuring the complete compilation of answer sheets of respondents-students regarding questionnaires, tests and practical assignments; as a practitioner-pedagogue, to express one's approach to the suitability of the ideas and principles of special methodology to practice, one's opinion on the current situation; to provide practical assistance to the researcher in assessing the level of methodological competence of the respondent-students based on educational cooperation.

A total of 6 practitioners-pedagogues recruited from higher education institutions selected as experimental areas took an active part in the process of organizing the experimental work. With their help, questionnaires, test questions, and special trainings were organized among the respondent-students.

Summary. Experimental work is considered the main link of scientific-pedagogical research, as in psychological and sociological research. Its correct organizational-management and practical-methodical organization creates the necessary conditions for the success of activities aimed at positively solving the research problem. In order for experimental work to be as effective as expected, it is first necessary to clearly define its purpose, correctly set scientific-pedagogical tasks, and choose effective methods wisely. These conditions were taken into account at the experimental stage of the scientific-pedagogical research aimed at solving the problem of developing methodical competence in future music teachers. As a result, the expected results were achieved.

References.

1. Aliboev T.Ch. Improvement of technologies for developing students' creativity qualities in an innovative educational environment (in the example of the subject "Technology"): ped.fanl. on ... fals.fanl. dr. (PhD) ... Diss. - Jizzakh: 2021. - p. 136.
2. Косяков Д.А. Факторы образования и воспитания // <https://zaochnik.com/spravochnik/pedagogika/teorija-vospitaniija/factory-vospitaniija>.

3. Тот источник: Косяков Д.А. Факторы образования и воспитания // <https://zaochnik.com/spravochnik/pedagogika/teorija-vospitanija/factory-vospitanija>.